

Welcome to the second HARPOCRATES newsletter!

We've prepared a lot of stuff for you - feel free to check out the latest happenings, meet the people behind the scenes, and maybe you'll find something interesting in our Zenodo space.

HARPOCRATES News

Shahid Raza Presents the HARPOCRATES Project at the 2023 Privacy Symposium Conference

Shahid Raza presented the HARPOCRATES Project at the 2023 Privacy Symposium Conference, held in Venice, Italy from 17 - 21 April, 2023. He is a cybersecurity expert from Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE) and serves as the Director of Cybersecurity at RISE. Raza holds a Master's degree in cybersecurity from KTH and an industrial PhD degree from Mälardalen University. He leads a team of 20+ technical security experts and played a key role in establishing RISE Cyber Range, a cybersecurity test and demo arena in Sweden.

[Learn More](#)

S2 Grupo Represents HARPOCRATES at ValgrAI Scientific Council Forum 2023

The ValgrAI Scientific Council Forum 2023, held at the Universitat Politècnica de València - Auditorio Cubo Azul on July 4, 2023, brought together experts, researchers, and industry professionals to discuss advancements and innovations in artificial intelligence (AI) research. The event was organized by valgrAI, the Valencian Graduate School and Research Network of Artificial Intelligence, with the aim of promoting collaboration and knowledge exchange within the AI community.

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HARPOCRATES Project at ECCC info day in Stockholm

On Friday, 16th June 2023, Nicolae Paladi from CanaryBit (CBIT) participated in the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC) Info Day held at Scandinavian XPO Arlanda, Sweden, and also available online for a global audience. This event, organized by the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre in collaboration with the ECCO (European Cybersecurity Community) project, aimed to foster a European cybersecurity community by providing information on crucial European calls and funding opportunities.

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HARPOCRATES at ESORICS and CPS4CIP 2023

Researchers Reyhaneh Rabbaninejad and Antonios Michalás from Tampere University (TUNI) presented the HARPOCRATES project at two conferences, ESORICS 2023 and CPS4CIP 2023. These events provided a platform where HARPOCRATES gained visibility and recognition among cybersecurity experts and practitioners.

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Cybersecurity and Data Privacy: An Interview with Nicolas Paladi of CanaryBit on the HARPOCRATES Project

In this edition, we're excited to introduce you to the HARPOCRATES project. We had the chance to chat with the project's CEO and co-founder of CanaryBit, who also leads the platform architecture team within HARPOCRATES. Dive into the technical aspects, objectives achieved so far, and the project's potential industry influence.

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Hackathon Secure the Valley

"Secure the Valley" Hackathon at the University of Zaragoza showcased Aragon's cybersecurity commitment, closely partnering with the Harpocrates Project. Computer experts analyzed Twitter data to identify users spreading regular or misleading comments. Originating from a cybersecurity directive, the event collaborated with Horizon Europe projects Harpocrates and Decido. Ana Isabel Prieto from S2Grupo provided datasets, and Luis Burdalo from S2 Grupo played a key role. This collaboration emphasized cybersecurity and innovation, fostering professional connections.

Experience the highlights of the "Secure the Valley" Hackathon and watch the video to get an inside look at the exciting event: <https://youtu.be/Gg15GrgppfE>

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Open Science

The HARPOCRATES project has established its community on Zenodo, a renowned research data repository and collaborative platform. Zenodo plays an important role in the dissemination of scientific knowledge by providing a space for researchers to archive and share their datasets, publications, and other research outputs openly and freely. Papers from HARPOCRATES researchers have already received 100+ downloads. This is the way that HARPOCRATES enhances the visibility of research but also ensures its long-term preservation and accessibility. To access the complete list of publications from the HARPOCRATES project, please visit the following link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/harpocrates-project/?page=1&size=20>.

Zenodo's commitment to open science aligns seamlessly with the project's goal of fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing within the scientific community.

The HARPOCRATES project is on Zenodo!

Join us on Zenodo and Be a Part of the HARPOCRATES Project!
Discover the Open Repository Transforming Research Visibility and Accessibility

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Deliverables

All of HARPOCRATES project's valuable deliverables are now available for direct access on our official website. These deliverables represent the culmination of extensive research and development efforts, offering practical insights and innovative solutions across various domains.

We encourage you to visit our website today and explore these resources. Whether you're a researcher seeking cutting-edge knowledge or someone interested in practical solutions, you'll find valuable information that can benefit your endeavors.

Don't miss out on the opportunity to access and utilize the HARPOCRATES project's deliverables to advance your own goals and projects.

[Learn More](#)

HARPOCRATES Consortium

The Harpocrates consortium is made up of 13 partners from 9 countries, including prestigious universities, research institutes, SMEs, and government bodies. The consortium will be coordinated by the Tampere University. It is expected that Harpocrates outcomes will include the development of open source algorithms and toolkits for secure data exchange in the government and healthcare sectors.

[Learn More](#)

Stay Tuned!

Stay updated on all our latest news, developments, research and general information regarding the HARPOCRATES project.

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